

Chinese Porcelain 'Embrechados' in Portuguese Garden Architecture

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Chinese porcelain began to be integrated into the decoration of Italian, Portuguese, and Spanish palace interiors in the 16th century, but the use of porcelain for exterior decoration, such as in garden architecture, cannot be observed in the early modern times outside Portugal. Intact porcelain plates and the cut out wells (bottoms) of plates and bowls would be stuck in the character of medallions on internal and external surfaces of garden pavilions, chapels, and fountains, with tiny pieces of broken borders applied together to fill out cartouches. This technique of applying shells, stones, rocks, crystals, pieces of glass, ceramics, and ferrous slag onto walls and ceilings is known in Portuguese as *embrechado*. Although analogous examples of this technique are to be found in other parts of Europe (the Grottenhof of the Munich Residence or the Nymphaeum in the Rosendael Castle in the Netherlands, for instance)—most notably in Italy—it was only in Portugal that Chinese porcelain was utilized. The influence of Italian Mannerist grottos, such as those of the Boboli Gardens and Villa di Castello in Florence, is evident in Portuguese examples. Nevertheless, grotto design in Italy had an important sculptural component: artists would resort to artificial stone to recreate a semblance of natural rock formations, as in the two Florentine examples. In contrast, artists in Portugal privileged the mosaic-like technique of *embrechado*, which allowed them to put forward the visual qualities of materials, such as the colour and shine of porcelain, crystals, and Oriental nacreous shells,

applied in abstract and figurative motives.

The earliest known historical reference to *embrechados* dates to around 1575 and concerns a fountain in the Hieronymites convent in Sintra, near Lisbon. A visitor reports seeing there 'a fountain which can justly be [considered] one of the most curious things of the house, richly and artificially adorned with conches, shells, scallops, small shining stones, and hundred things more' (Villalba y Estaña, 2002, p. 95). However, the earliest recorded use of Chinese porcelain for *embrechados* comes from two preserved examples dated to the second or third decade of the 17th century. These are *casas de fresco*—small garden pavilions provided with a fountain and a bench, used for rest during warm summer days—fitted in imitation of a grotto in the gardens of Sanches Baena in Vila Viçosa and the Counts of Basto palace grounds in Évora. The first combines Italianate stuccos and frescoes of arabesques, grotesques, putti, vines and garlands of fruits, and flowers on the cupola with *embrechados* made of shells, stones, and porcelain. The walls of the *casa de fresco* in Évora bear coats-of-arms of military religious orders (e.g., Order of Santiago, Knights Templar) made from *embrechados*, but only the cross of the Military Order of Aviz is composed of the most precious material: blue-and-white porcelain. It is not coincidental, as before it became property of the Counts of Basto, the medieval castle of Évora belonged to this Portuguese order of chivalry. The commissioner of the pavilion, Diogo de

Fig. 1 *Embrechados* at garden elevation of sacristy and chapel, Henriques Palace, Alcáçovas

Castro (1560–1640), aimed to present himself as the heir of the *reconquistadores* who fought against the Moorish rule of Iberia.

The most exuberant and startling *embrechado* decoration by far is that of the chapel and garden of the Henriques Palace in Alcáçovas, created around 1640 to 1660 by Henrique Henriques, 7th Senhor of Alcáçovas (1601–85). The garden elevation of the chapel and sacristy, as well as their interiors (excluding a wainscot of painted Portuguese tiles, or azulejos), are completely covered in *embrechados* made of nacreous shells, stones, Chinese porcelain, Portuguese faience, and glass (Fig. 1). Porcelain shards are to be seen in other parts of the garden as well: on a wall articulated by three niches bordering the pond, and on the ceiling of the galilee, both structures being entirely covered with *embrechados*. Tiny shards have been used to fill out cartouches, along with wells of dishes or bowls to emphasize the articulation of surfaces. In the chapel, porcelain has been knowingly placed in a way that bestows symbolical meaning onto the material: it fills the cartouche with a representation of the dove of the

Holy Spirit (Fig. 2), and the ceiling with a personified image of the Sun (Fig. 3). Lastly, the altar niche was originally richly covered with porcelain (meant to set the background for a Golgotha placed in the altar), of which, most notably, three wells of Jiajing (1522–66) or Wanli (1573–1620) period dishes are extant today. In these instances, the shine and the blue-and-white colour of the porcelain is thus used to symbolize the heavens. The porcelain used in Alcáçovas comes from the Jiajing, Longqing (1567–72), and Wanli periods (Silva, 2012), such as the six insides of 'crow' (tall) cups with a bird-on-a-rock motif (Rinaldi, 1989, pp. 142–45, 153–58) inserted around a circular cartouche; it therefore predates by some decades the commission of the decoration.

It is the profusion of Alcáçovas *embrechados* that staggers the viewer, but a truly elegant and sophisticated example of an *embrechado* design is to be found in the garden of the Palace of the Marquises of Fronteira in Lisbon. The residence was built by 1669 on the outskirts of Lisbon, by João de Mascarenhas, 1st Marquis of Fronteira (1633–81). Initially the garden had two *casas de fresco* decorated

Fig. 2 Cartouche with the dove of the Holy Spirit, chapel, Henriques Palace, Alcáçovas

Fig. 3 Ceiling of the chapel, Henriques Palace, Alcáçovas

with porcelain shards, one of which has not been preserved. The latter was located inside a thorn or laurel labyrinth, in a 'wood with winding paths, coiling in on itself' (Carita, 1990, p. 111), and was structurally part of it, as it was composed of stone columns supporting a construction made of laurel branches and other evergreen plants. It was fitted with a pyramid-shaped fountain made of pieces of Chinese porcelain, glass, shells, and pearls, which, in the words of a 1678 description, ejected 'water in the form of an open crown, giving rise to a pond that is decorated in various colours; nearby is a bed prepared for you to lie down if you fancy taking a siesta on a summer day, while aligning your sleep with the sound of the water slowly falling' (Carita, 1990, p. 111).

Today, three preserved ensembles of porcelain *embrechados* are to be found in a *casa de fresco*, the vestibule of the chapel, and on a fountain. The *casa de fresco* is a circular, domed building with an arched facade surmounted by a pediment with two

side pinnacles and the coat-of-arms of Madalena de Castro, 1st Marquise of Fronteira (which suggests she was the commissioner of the pavilion) (Fig. 4). Its interior (see Fig. 5) is articulated by sixteen niches, three of which contain fountains in the form of a satyr, a faun, and a griffin. In the 1678 description it was curiously described as 'a small refectory' (ibid.), which points to its function as a sort of dining or refreshment room that could accommodate a large group, being fitted with a total of ten benches in the niches. It was thus most likely used for social gatherings.

The chapel's vestibule is architecturally an integral and final element of the 'Gallery of the Arts', an open terrace decorated with statues that connects the residence to the chapel. On the right-hand side, the vestibule is enclosed by a wide arch with a rather classical *embrechado* design, bearing resemblance to the decoration of the barrel vault of the Madama Grotto in the Boboli Gardens (Fig. 7). Since the vestibule's facade is articulated in the form

of a so-called 'Serlian window', it has been said that the vestibule was inspired by architectural patterns of Sebastiano Serlio (1475–c. 1554) and Andrea Palladio (1508–1590) (Mesquita 1992, p. 376) (Fig. 6). However, it seems a rather direct assimilation of two specific buildings: namely, the nymphaeum loggia in Rome's Villa Giulia, designed by Bartolomeo Ammanati (1511–92), and the mid-15th century vestibule of the Pazzi Chapel in Florence, attributed to Filippo Brunelleschi (1377–1446). The Pazzi Chapel was, nota bene, richly decorated with terracotta sculptures by Luca della Robbia (c.1400–82), emulated here in the Gallery of the Arts by blue-and-white medallions of Roman emperors enclosed in colourful faience fruit garlands.

An azulejo wainscot decorates the facade and the interiors of both the *casa de fresco* and the vestibule, while porcelain, stone, glass, coral, and shells cover all the other surfaces (upper walls, pediment, ceiling of the grotto, arches, pilasters, entablatures, niche vaults). The cut out wells of porcelain plates are the key element structuring the interior. By means of their symmetrical placement in cartouches along the central axes of pilasters, arches, niches, and abutments and in the false voussoirs of arches, the display underlines the perfectly classical articulation

Fig. 5 Interior, *casa de fresco*, Palace of the Marquises of Fronteira, Lisbon

Fig. 4 Exterior of the *casa de fresco* of the Palace of the Marquises of Fronteira, Lisbon

of the interiors, which, in turn, contrasts with its un-classically playful lacework décor. Porcelain 'medallions' are placed in the same fashion as, for example, della Robbia's medallions in the aforementioned Florentine chapel, which accounts for their classicizing function. Small and large, rare and common pieces are skilfully juxtaposed. Their placement reflects the tension between their perceived singularity and seriality: insides with representations of flower vases, human figures, deer, monkeys, and birds are singularized through placement in shell medallions, right on the axes of the niches' vaults, whereas commoner 'crow' cup wells abound on the ceiling of the *casa de fresco*.

Interestingly, the iconography of the azulejos in the chapel's vestibule (which include grotesque herms, tritons, birds in tree crowns, Bacchus playing the guitar) does not allude in any way to the sacred space it precedes; rather, the chapel appears as yet another garden pavilion, an imaginative amalgam

Fig. 6 Vestibule of the chapel, Palace of the Marquises of Fronteira, Lisbon

of both religious and secular architectural patterns. Both azulejos and porcelain pieces chosen for decoration refer to the realms of fauna and flora, to leisure and pleasure found in the bosom of nature, and to the metamorphoses and the playfulness of nature itself. The porcelain's iconography echoes elements of the surrounding garden: birds, rocks, water, flowers. Some azulejo panels in the *casa de fresco* represent grotesque satyr, faun, and mermaid herms (tapered pillars with a portrait bust) with plant-like features and large non-European-looking earrings decorated with leaves. Others show birds such as parrots, pawns, owls, and magpies—different species in every niche—sitting in blossoming trees against a mountainous landscape, a pattern inspired by the iconography of Indian textiles, often used in the decoration of altarpieces in Portugal. The benches of the niches are clad with azulejos representing mascarons, or architectural ornaments of faces, some of which feature attributes that can be found on porcelains displayed above them: ribbons,

insects, sprays of peaches, and birds. The notion of metamorphosis is thematized in the images of herms (a common motif in grotto iconography, such as at the 16th century Villa Giulia built for Pope Julius III) and through the constant references to water: the obvious connection of a *casa de fresco* with a water source, the iconography of the displayed porcelain (aquatic plants, birds swimming in water), and its material features of shine, coldness, and blue-and-white coloration, which allude to the characteristics of water itself. A beholder would be also constantly surrounded by the sound of running water, judging by the astounding number of fountains in the garden described in historical sources.

The majority of the 192 porcelain wells of bowls and plates used in the decoration of the *casa de fresco* (152), fountain (17), and chapel vestibule (23) date to the Jiajing and Wanli periods, including the notable group of 47 Kraak 'crow' cups. Some pieces were added later as replacements, for example, the well of a 'Canton blue' plate from the mid-19th

century (Silva, 2015, p. 100). Among the 'medallions' it was possible to identify the following:

–The well of a plate with four geese: three sitting on land near water and another flying beside two peonies, lotuses, and rushes; second half of the 16th century (Pinto de Matos, 1996, cat. 15) (Fig. 8)

–Two rare wells of plates with a landscape, deer, and monkey, drawn with great attention to detail; Jiajing period, mid-16th century (Pinto de Matos et al., eds, 1997, cat. 12; Krahl, 1986, vol. II, cat. 874) (see Fig. 9)

–Well of a plate with two roosters, two peonies, and a fence in the background; Jiajing period,

Fig. 8 Well of a plate with four geese, in white porcelain with underglaze blue from the Ming dynasty (1368–1644), second half of the 16th century

Fig. 7 Fountain in the chapel's vestibule, Palace of the Marquises of Fronteira, Lisbon

Fig. 9 Well of a plate with monkey and deer, in white porcelain with underglaze blue from the Jiajing period (1522–66), mid-16th century

mid-16th century (Pinto de Matos, 1996, cat. 14; Krahl, 1986, vol. II, cat. 887)

–Two wells of plates with two deer, a pine tree, and peaches; Wanli period, c. 1595–1606 (Vinhais and Welsh, 2008, cat. 13) (see Fig. 10)

We would like to signalize other interesting and yet unstudied porcelain *embrechado* ensembles, many of which are on private property and thus not easy to access: they decorate ponds in Quinta da

Fig. 10 Well of a plate with deer, pine, and peaches, in white porcelain with underglaze blue from the Wanli period (1573–1620), c. 1595–1606

Água Férrea in Belas, a niche and fountain in Quinta da Nossa Senhora da Conceição in Barcarena, two chapels in Quinta da Penha Verde in Sintra, and a *casa de fresco* in Quinta das Lapas in Monte Redondo. In the 18th century, enamelled Chinese porcelain began to be utilized as well: famille verte, rouge de fer, Imari, and famille rose porcelain in a *casa de fresco* in Quinta da Ribeirinha in Camarate (Silva, 2015); famille rose porcelain in the fountains of the palaces of Marquis of Pombal in Lisbon and Oeiras from the 1760s; and Kangxi period (1662–1722) red-enamelled porcelain in the *casa de fresco* of the convent of São Paulo de Alferrara in Palmela. The latter pavilion, from around 1725 to 1750, featured a saint source and a saint image. Conventual *casas de fresco* covered with *embrechados* to resemble artificial grottoes were most likely meant as references to the grottoes of hermit saints dedicated to meditation and prayer (Serrão and Meco, 2007), therefore it is not a coincidence that the religious orders which made use of such decorations were eremitic (Albergaria, 1997, p. 481): Franciscans (Sintra, Arrábida), Hieronymites (Sintra), and Paulines (Palmela and Redondo).

The majority of these porcelain *embrechado* decorations were found in and around the cities of Lisbon and Évora, in *quintas* (residences built in the countryside and designated for leisure and farming) and in convents (see Fig. 11). They were especially used in garden architecture (*casas de fresco*, ponds, fountains, niches, and chapels), both in secular and religious spaces, and in places of sociability and solitary meditation. If they decorated interiors, these were always distant from the functional core

of the premises. The consistent connection between *embrechados* and the realms of water, on the one hand, and spirituality on the other, is also very meaningful.

According to present knowledge, porcelain started to be integrated within *embrechados* around 1620, but the pinnacle of this technique dates to the mid- to late 17th century. Most of the porcelain pieces are dated to the Wanli period, which suggests that porcelain procured for *embrechados* could not have been acquired directly from ship cargoes damaged during the voyage from Asia, as they predate by a handful of decades the creation of *embrechado* decors. The porcelain, therefore, might have belonged to the commissioners and, either already partly damaged or intact, been made into pieces deliberately by workshops or artists realizing such decorations. It might also have been acquired by the workshops themselves, along with all the other materials. Artists would try to procure them at the lowest cost, thus second-hand and already defective. Porcelain reached Portugal in relatively large quantities in the 16th and early 17th centuries, but it was still a luxury product and continued as such into the 18th century. As a result, there probably existed a market for wares damaged over decades of use, but still considered too precious to be simply thrown away.

Characteristic to the very technique of Portuguese mosaic-like *embrechados* was the focus on the visual effects of materials, like shine and colour, which made porcelain especially coveted and suited for this purpose. Porcelain was treated in *embrechados* in a twofold manner: either conspicuous or discreet. On the one hand, unlike materials such as shells, stones, and glass, it was placed on articulating architectural elements (friezes, arches, pediments, entablature) in the form of carefully cut out medallions. It therefore had the function of structuring and classicizing the decorated surfaces, which accounts for porcelain's exceptional status. The iconography carried by wells of plates or bowls (especially of floral, vegetal, and animal character) also could impact the perception of the whole design and of the space's function. For example, the fountain in the Pombal Palace in Oeiras is decorated with *embrechados* suggesting the trellis of an Italianate flower pergola, whereas the Qianlong period (1736–96) famille rose plates stuck to the niche's vault are painted in flowers themselves. The iconography of the porcelain objects participates here in the illusion that is being created through the

Fig. 11 Map with known cases of porcelain *embrechados* in residences (blue) and convents (red)
Image by Joanna Ciemińska in ArcGIS Pro

design. On the other hand, regardless of whether the wares put into pieces were already damaged or not, the use of dozens or hundreds of tiny shards as wall decoration alongside local shells and stones attests to the unparalleled familiarity of the Portuguese with Chinese porcelain, a casualness that did not occur in grotto design anywhere else in Europe. Used in this way, porcelain is not treated differently than other materials, although it should be noted that the placement of shard-filled cartouches could also be meaningful in how it underscored specific elements—such was the case of the ceiling and altar decoration in the chapel in Alcáçovas or the *casas de fresco* in Évora and Vila Viçosa, where porcelain frames the recently granted coat-of-arms of the owner and forms a Christian cross.

All photographs are by the author.

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